
Integrated pest management—other pests

Rat damage in ricefields under dry field conditions in Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

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We surveyed crop losses to rats *Bandicota bengalensis* (Gray) and *Rattus*

rattus (Linnaeus) in ricefields under dry farming conditions in Rewa District. Most of the fields had narrow, small bunds and a light soil. Drought conditions prevailed during the wet crop season. IR36 and local varieties Biranjphul, Kabeli, Dhiula, Lohandi, and Dilhansa were broadcast seeded.

We observed 26 fields, each 0.4-1.0 ha, before maturity of the standing crop when soil was completely dry. Two fields per village were selected to record the

number of hills and the healthy/damaged tillers in five randomly selected 1-m² samples along a diagonal line/field.

Average yield of 100 panicles was determined at harvest and multiplied by the number of damaged tillers to get the yield loss due to rats.

Rats cut 1.4-7.2 tillers/m² before the maturity stage of the crop. Yield loss was 1.3-6.7%. Estimated yield loss was 2.33-12.02 g/m², with a mean of 6.08 g/m² (60.8 kg/ha). □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

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Individuals, institutions, and organizations are requested to inform the editor about upcoming events in rice research or related fields for the Rice Dateline. Send announcements to the Editor, IRRN, International Rice Research Institute, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. □

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September

- 5-25 Main Phase of the 4th External IRRI Review. IRRI. Contact M.F.L. Goon/K.A. Gomez, IRRI.
- 15 Sep-2 Oct Senior Advanced Course on Lowland Development. Delft, The Netherlands. Contact International Institute for Hydraulic and Environmental Engineering, Oude Delft 95, P.O. Box 3015, 2601 DA Delft, The Netherlands.
- 21-25 IRRI Board of Trustees Meeting. IRRI. Contact K.J. Lampe, IRRI.
- 28 Sep-2 Oct Asian Rice Farming Systems Working Group Meeting. Suweon, Korea. Contact V.R. Carangal/F.A. Bernardo, IRRI.
- 28 Sep-16 Oct Effective Irrigation Management Course. University of Southampton, United Kingdom. Contact Course Administrator, Effective Irrigation Management Short Course, Institute of Irrigation Studies, The University, Southampton SO9 5NH, United Kingdom. Fax: 0703-593017.

October

- 12-16 Indo-China Rice Research Meeting. Vientiane, Laos. Contact J.M. Schiller/V.R. Carangal, IRRI.
- 15-16 Sri Lanka-IRRI Work Plan Meeting. Contact F.A. Bernardo/V.R. Carangal/D. Senadhira, IRRI.
- 19-23 Madagascar Work Plan Meeting. Contact F.A. Bernardo/G.L. Denning, IRRI.

November

- 11-13 Sri Lanka Work Plan Meeting at IRRI. Contact F.A. Bernardo/D. Senadhira/G.L. Denning, IRRI.
- 16-20 International Workshop on Women in Rice Farming Systems, Chiang Mai, Thailand. Contact V.R. Carangal/T. Paris, IRRI.
- 25-27 Bhutan-IRRI Work Plan Meeting. Contact F.A. Bernardo/G.L. Denning, IRRI.

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